

Communication of the healthcare sector on climate change: A quantitative study with exploratory observations

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Abstract

This study examines the external communication of the German healthcare system regarding climate change up until June 2024, utilizing a systematic quantitative content analysis. The study analyses websites, position papers, press releases, and social media platforms (Facebook, Instagram, and “X”/Twitter) from 42 organizations across various sectors of the healthcare system (a total of 54 organizations analyzed). Content categories were developed based on a review of topic-specific literature. Only a few contributions (<10 press releases/year) prior to 2018 were identified. Since 2018, there has been a highly significant increase and diversification in external communication, differentiated by communication channels and thematic areas. Overall, a relatively homogeneous communication pattern among the various sectors is evident. The contributions primarily address sector-specific climate adaptation and mitigation measures (49% of cases), followed by measures aimed at individuals (19%) and moderate calls for Enhanced climate policy measures (15%). The multiple cited behavioral economic communication approaches linking climate- and health-protective behaviors were identifiable in only 2.5% of cases; similarly, tipping points in ecosystems were communicated only seldom (0.3%).

1 Introduction

The climate crisis represents the greatest threat to human health [1, 2]. In 2024, global surface temperatures reached +1.5°C above pre-industrial levels for the first time, and current measurements raise concerns about rapid planetary warming [3, 4, 5]. Modern healthcare systems face immense challenges in transitioning to sustainable mitigation strategies and adapting to changing environmental conditions (cf. *Planetary Health* [1, 6, 7]).

Professional knowledge and risk communication by the healthcare sector have become increasingly significant, particularly in light of digitalization and shifting communication patterns [8, 9, 10]. The central question arises: How can people be effectively informed about health risks, climate-adaptive behaviors, and comprehensive societal solutions in the context of prevention?

It is presumed that individuals with low readiness to act (RTA)¹ are less likely to actively seek information. While the vast majority of the

¹ *Readiness to act* refers to the willingness to take action in response to climate change. It encompasses individual behavior, acceptance of climate-protective measures and political participation.

German population (84%) stays informed about recent news [11], 30–34% do not, and an additional 26–27% engage with information on climate change only occasionally, according to other studies [10]. This risk awareness contrasts with the actual health risks posed by the climate crisis. Based on a recurring study, the risk awareness showed little change between 2022 and 2024 [12].

Despite widespread global support for climate protection measures (Globally: 86%; Germany: 85.6%), the need for comprehensive climate protection measures is widely recognized and is largely supported by a majority of the society [13, 14]. A potential strategy to increase RTA may involve the utilization of health narratives to minimize perceived personal distance from the effects of climate change, emphasizing the positive co-benefits and providing concrete action strategies tailored to specific audiences [1, 10, 15, 16, 17]. However, it must be emphasized that information alone is insufficient to drive behavioral change and may even backfire by fostering a sense of threat fatigue. Factors such as social (and cultural) norms, trust, perceived effectiveness of measures, self-efficacy, and psychological barriers must also be taken into account [12, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23]. Another aspect under investigation is the political dimension of the climate crisis [24, 25, 26, 27, 28] and the healthcare sector's role in addressing it [29, 30]. Historically, this sector has played a pivotal role in addressing humanitarian crises, pandemics, and life-threatening diseases such as smallpox due to a combination of moral authority, professional prestige, and evidence-based paradigms [15]. This study also examines the formulation of climate policy demands, as well as the potential contextualization and factual assessment of climate protests, which are frequently covered by the media.

Both climate change and the communication of knowledge and risks are highly complex phenomena that vary depending on the medium and target audience. Even though communication of health risks related to climate change must be directed at our society as a

whole, the diverse media consumption patterns of different demographic groups must be taken into account [11, 31]. Germany has some governance approaches as well as a comparatively detailed risk assessment of the impacts of climate change; However, the responsibilities within the self-administration of the healthcare system are also equally complex and heterogeneously distributed [1]. Although some international literature exists on health-specific communication strategies and media analyses of climate crisis-related health risks, no studies were identified that specifically address implementation within the German healthcare system. The present study seeks to bridge that gap by analyzing publicly available posts from a diverse range of sources in the German healthcare system.

2 Methodology

Data collection was conducted using a quantitative content analysis. Formal and thematic categories were developed deductively and defined in a codebook. A total of $n = 996$ contributions from 54 organizations were systematically analyzed (no contributions could be found for 12 organizations). The collected data were processed using the software *R*. Systematic data collection was conducted between March 2023 and July 2024. Values for 2024 (from June 1 to June 30, 2024) were doubled to account for partial data and are presented separately. Unexpected and non-measurable observations were noted during data collection.

An example of data collection can be found in the supplement.

Hypothesis 1: Change in the total number of publications on climate change over the periods under consideration (quantity)

H₀: The total number of external communications on climate change has not changed.

H₁: The total number of external communications on climate change has changed.

Hypothesis 2: Change in the topics addressed in external communication on climate change (topics)

H₀: The topics addressed in external communication on climate change have not changed.

H₁: The topics addressed in external communication on climate change have changed.

The analysis focused on established health organizations in Germany whose founding purpose does not explicitly include promoting mitigation or adaptation. The selection of organizations was based on two criteria: (1) relevance, such as the size of the associated professional group, public recognition, and voting rights within self-governance, and (2) the aim of examining the most heterogeneous sectors possible (categorized into groups) to increase external validity. A separate group (“Other”) includes organizations related to healthcare services but which are not directly part of the legally defined healthcare system or its professional associations. The state medical and dental associations were examined in order to analyze implementation in comprehensive care. Otherwise, only the federal association was examined.

The selection of analyzed platforms was based on (1) reach and (2) methodological compatibility. Due to partially inconsistent digitization, relevant print media and magazines were not included in the analysis. Both websites (content on webpages, position papers, and press releases) and social media profiles on Facebook, Instagram, and “X”/Twitter were examined. Social media platforms primarily focused on video formats (e.g., YouTube, TikTok) were excluded from the study. Due to the need for analyzing textual content formulations and reviewing accompanying images on social media, web crawlers were not employed.

The development of formal categories (Figure 1) allows for insights into the respective communication medium and its temporal trends. The thematic categories (Figure 2),

developed based on a non-systematic interdisciplinary literature review, are grouped into thematic clusters: risk awareness, solution strategies, and political articulation. The groups serve as an overview and are compared due to overlaps in content. Contributions can fulfil multiple thematic categories. Certain communication strategies, such as linking health protection to climate protection or creating personal relevance, are challenging to measure due to indirect formulations and subjective interpretation and were thus not defined in the codebook.

Figure 1
Overview over the formal categories for the quantitative content analysis differentiating the sources that were considered for analysis.

Source	Formal categories
Website	Date of publication
	Website content
	Position paper
	Press
Social Media	Facebook
	Instagram
	Twitter / “X”

Figure 2
Overview over the thematic categories for the quantitative content analysis. These were defined after analysis of the contents of each included post/ publication.

Cluster	Thematic categories
Risk awareness	Existential / Greatest Threat to Human Health
	Tipping Points
Solution / action strategies	Sector-specific measures
	Individual measures
	Co-Benefits
	Emissions Health Care System
	Transition away from fossil fuels
Political Participation	Strengthened climate policy
	Insufficiency of climate policy
	Addressing climate protests
	Participation in climate protests

3 Results

The results show a significant increase in media contributions related to climate change (comparison of total numbers for 2022 and 2023: $t = -2.92$, $p = 0.009$, Fig. 2). Before 2018, climate change was only minimally addressed, primarily from the German Red Cross. Between 2019 and 2023, a steep increase (1055%) and diversification of communication channels and content can be observed (Fig. 3 - 5).

Figure 3:

A line chart depicts the absolute number of yearly contributions on climate communication in the health sector from 2008 to 2024. Contributions remain consistently low from 2008 to 2018 before rising sharply from 2019 onward. The steepest increase occurs between 2019 and 2023, with a 1055% growth over this period. The 2024 data is partially estimated based on available contributions during data collection and is represented with dashed lines.

Figure 4:

A line chart illustrates the absolute number of yearly contributions on climate communication within various health sector groups from 2008 to 2024. The chart differentiates six groups: professional policy/interest representation, state medical and dental associations, rescue services, health insurance companies, G-BA members, and others. Contributions remain consistently low across all groups until 2018, followed by a sharp rise from 2019 onward. State medical and dental associations show the steepest increase, peaking in 2023. The most significant growth occurs between 2019 and 2023, with a 1055% increase. The 2024 data is partially estimated based on available contributions during data collection and is represented with dashed lines.

Figure 5:

A point plot visualizes the number and distribution of climate-related contributions by source (e.g., websites, position papers, press, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter/X) and topic (e.g., threat, tipping points, sector-specific measures, individual measures, co-benefits, emissions, strengthened climate policy, insufficiency of climate policy, addressing climate protests, participation in climate protests) from 2008 to 2024. The color gradient indicates contribution frequency, ranging from light blue (low) to dark red (high). The plot reveals a significant increase in contributions across all categories after 2018, with websites and press as the dominant sources. Topics like sector-specific measures, individual measures, and strengthened climate policy appear most frequently, while participation in and addressing climate protests

remain less prominent.

All examined communication channels are being utilized (Fig. 6). The contributions primarily address sector-specific climate adaptation and mitigation measures (~49% of cases), often in combination with mentions of the emissions of the healthcare system (10%) (Fig. 7). Regarding risk communication, climate change was identified as the greatest or an existential health threat in 5.6% of cases. However, only 0.3% of the analyzed contributions addressed tipping points in the ecosystem. Individual measures or climate-adapted behaviors were addressed in 19% of cases, while the call for the transition away from fossil fuels was rarely mentioned (2.1%). The widely cited communication approaches emphasizing the co-benefits of climate and health protection were identifiable in only 2.5% of cases.

Figure 6:

A) A bar chart presents the distribution of contributions across formal categories, shown in absolute numbers and percentages.
B) A line plot depicts the development of contributions per formal category per year between 2008 -2024. The 2024 data is partially estimated based on available contributions during data collection and is represented with dashed lines.

Figure 7

A) A bar chart displays the distribution of topics by absolute numbers and percentages across eleven thematic categories. Examples of contributions classified into each category are provided in the supplements.
B) A line plot illustrates the development of topics across all analyzed contributions over time. A sharp increase in mentions of sector-specific measures is evident from 2020 onward.

Regarding political articulation, calls for stronger climate protection efforts by the federal government are evident (19%). Sharp condemnation of climate policy is the exception (1.3%), as are references to climate protests (2.2%) or active participation in climate protection protests (1.1%). The contributions can primarily be attributed to a trade union (marburger Bund) and Doctors without borders (MSF) Germany. Overall, a relatively heterogeneous external communications evident among the groups. Political content is less prevalent on social media (Fig. 8).

Figure 8

A) Heatmaps visualize the distribution of publications across formal and thematic categories. Darker red indicates a higher number of publications within a category combination, while light beige signifies no publications for that combination.

B) Heatmaps show the distribution of all dataset publications across formal and thematic categories.

C) Heatmaps illustrate the distribution of dataset publications across health system organizations within formal and thematic categories.

A)

State-Level Medical/Dental Associations

Rescue service

Professional Political Interest Representations

Members of the G-BA

Health insurance providers

Other

B)

Health care system (total)

C)

Total

3. 2 Additional observations

The following observations, though not included in the study design, emerged as relevant during the quantitative content analysis.

1. Health insurance companies' contributions were primarily individual-centered and minimally political. Among all examined groups, their profiles received the highest engagement, with several thousand views and likes per post. In contrast, organizations from other groups saw interactions ranging from one to three digits.

2. Health organizations are not apolitical. A significant number of posts addressed expressions of solidarity with gender diversity and posts against right-wing extremism.

3. Contributions related to the undefined "sector-specific measures" largely focused on increasing heat stress or climate protection efforts within the healthcare system. Overall, there is little differentiation in risk communication. Existing governance approaches, such as collaboration with the EU, the National Prevention Conference (NPK), or the Public Health Service (ÖGD), were not communicated.

4. The external communication shows a limited connection between abstract risk indicators and personal experiences of extreme weather events. Extreme weather events in Germany (e.g., recurring floods in the Ahr Valley since 2021) were communicated but were not linked to climate change.

5. Only demonstrations were considered in the analyzed posts (e.g. Fridays for Future). Acts of civil disobedience or corresponding organizations (e.g. Extinction Rebellion, Just stop Oil, Last Generation) were not addressed.

6. The addressing of a public health approach or social inequalities (e.g., climate justice) was minimal and only presented by a few organizations. Mainly, posts from the DRK (German Red Cross) and MSF Germany referenced climate-related damages in countries of the Global South.

4 Discussion

The study design is based on findings related to media usage and changing communication patterns, such as the growing significance of the internet and social media as communication sources, the relevance of public service media in climate change-related information behavior, and the high trust in professional groups and websites of health actors. The study design allows for a differentiated analysis of external communication. However, there is insufficient consideration of content-related categories such as the communication of concrete action options within risk communication, the articulation of social inequalities, and the categorization of global/local risk indicators. The communication approaches identified were discovered during the literature research, the publication date of which was after the codebook was defined. It is important to note that the object of study encompasses a representative number of organizations from various sectors, but only a subset of the healthcare sector and communication channels. Authorities and state institutions that are not part of the healthcare structures but are related to healthcare and play a central role in raising social awareness and promoting climate protection and adaptation measures (e.g., the Public Health Service [ÖGD], the Federal Centre for Health Education [BZgA], or the Robert Koch Institute [RKI]), were not part of this study.

During data collection, the following methodological issues arose:

1. The boundaries between the topic of climate change and other aspects of the ecological crisis, such as biodiversity loss, were sometimes fluid and difficult to differentiate. Corresponding aspects were only marginally mentioned.
2. Some posts focused on educating about heat stress, which might suggest raising awareness about the health impacts of climate change but did not explicitly mention or link to climate change. These posts were not analyzed.
3. Furthermore, the analysis of the social media platform "X" revealed that many health actors posted evaluative reposts, whose original

sources were not part of the study's scope. For methodological accuracy, only posts from the examined organizations were analyzed. Consequently, additional posts from the source were found, but were not included in the data.

4. During the study period, dynamic changes in user behavior and social media platform administration were observed. Since 2024, Instagram's algorithm filters out political content from profiles that are neither subscribed to nor actively searched for ("shadow banning" [32]). On the "X" platform, changes in moderation and content management following the acquisition by Elon Musk led to various organizations ceasing their activities.

5. In the analysis of the Facebook platform, some profiles could not be fully loaded and analysed due to technical issues. These problems are likely related to the website provider rather than the performance of the device used.

6. Due to the aforementioned issues, only a limited proportion of postings from each source were analyzed. Therefore, the total number of posts output by each source needs to be considered as a potential confound of the results.

5 Conclusion

Climate change poses existential health risks and significant challenges for the healthcare sector. The systematic expansion of awareness regarding the etiology of health and prevention through mitigation can be fostered by targeted, audience-oriented communication strategies. In the German healthcare system, climate change has only recently started to receive the necessary attention in communication efforts.

Most of the health organizations analysed communicate about climate change. The initial hypotheses regarding the quantitative and qualitative changes in the healthcare sector's external communication on climate change have been confirmed. The study's results show a significant increase in the analyzed contributions starting from 2018 (1055% increase between 2019 and 2023). Since 2018, both the communication channels and the topics addressed have diversified significantly. The primary communication approaches focus on sector-specific measures for implementing mitigation and adaptation strategies (49% of contributions), promoting individual mitigation and adaptive behaviors (19%), and calls for political action (15%). Overall, a relatively homogeneous external communication is observable across communication channels and healthcare sectors. Despite their frequent emphasis in literature, behavioral economic communication approaches linking climate- and health-protective behaviors (so called "Co-Benefits") are communicated only to a limited extent (2.5% of contributions).

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Supplements

Table for the absolute number by groups and organizations (source)

Organisation	Absolute Frequency	Website	Press	Position paper	Instagram	Facebook	X / Twitter
State-Level Medical/Dental Associations	341	120	48	3	94	41	92
Landesärztekammer Bayern	35	22	2	1	8	-	-
LÄK Baden-Württemberg	53	39	-	-	-	-	14
LÄK Berlin	79	-	10	-	26	-	53
LÄK Brandenburg	-*	-	-	-	-	-	-
LÄK Bremen	23	10	-	-	-	13	-
LÄK Hamburg	44	1	-	-	20	11	12
LÄK Hessen	11	2	-	-	-	5	4
LÄK Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	1	-	1	-	-	-	-
LÄK Niedersachsen	11	2	2	1	-	2	4
LÄK Nordrhein- Westfalen*	29	6	6	-	22	1	-
LÄK Saarland	7	-	7	-	-	-	-
LÄK Rheinland-Pfalz	2	-	1	-	-	-	-
LÄK Sachsen	11	-	10	-	1	-	-
LÄK Sachsen-Anhalt	6	3	2	-	1	-	-
LÄK Schleswig-Holstein	15	1	3	-	7	5	-
LÄK Thüringen	2	-	2	-	-	-	-
Landeszahnärztekammer Bayern	4	4	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Baden-Württemberg	2	2	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Berlin	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Brandenburg	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	3	-	-	-	1	-	2
LZÄK Niedersachsen	2	-	-	-	-	-	2
LZÄK Nordrhein	3	-	-	-	1	2	-
LZÄK Saarland	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Sachsen-Anhalt	1	-	-	-	-	1	-
LZÄK Schleswig-Holstein	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Sachsen	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Members of the G-BA	45	2	14	1	9	0	19
Kassenärztliche Bundesvereinigung (KBV)	4	1	-	-	2	-	1
Gemeinsamer Bundesausschuss (G-BA)	1	1	-	-	-	-	-
Deutsche Krankengesellschaft (DKG)	17	-	10	-	7	-	1
GKV-Spitzenverband (GKV)	23	-	4	1	-	-	18
Kassenzahnärztliche Bundesvereinigung	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Health Insurance Providers	103	21	30	-	25	17	11
Techniker Krankenkasse (TK)	11	1	5	-	5	3	2
Allgemein Ortskrankenkasse (AOK)	22	4	6	-	12	-	-
Barmer Ersatzkasse (BARMER)	26	8	3	-	5	11	-
Deutsche Angestellten-Krankenkasse (DAK)	12	4	-	-	-	-	8
IKK Classic	13	1	8	-	2	2	-
Kaufmännische Krankenkasse (KKH)	19	3	8	-	3	2	3
Emergency Services	197	39	52	1	74	20	11
Deutsches Rotes Kreuz (DRK)	136	13	52	-	54	16	1
Malteser	26	-	-	-	17	2	7
Johanniter	35	26	-	1	3	2	3
Professional Political Interest Representations	124	3	23	11	16	14	57
Bundesärztekammer (BÄK)	64	1	3	2	12	-	46
Bundeszahnärztekammer (BZÄK)	6	1	4	1	-	-	-
Hartmannbund	33	-	5	5	2	10	11
Marburger Bund	79	1	54	-	10	12	3
Bundespsychotherapeutenkammer (BPTK)	8	1	4	1	-	-	-
Bundesver. Deutscher Apothekerverbände (ABDA)	13	-	7	-	2	4	-
Bundespflegekammer	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subtotal	895	161	214	15	220	104	188
Other	103	21	7	-	38	17	20
AWMF	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Verbund unabhängiger Heilpraktiker (VUH)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bund Deutscher Heilpraktiker (BDH)	28	11	-	-	-	17	-
Ärzte ohne Grenzen Deutschland (MSF)	75	10	7	-	38	-	20
Total	996	182	221	15	258	121	208

* For better readability, results with entries marked as "-" were replaced.

** The contributions from the State Medical Associations of North Rhine and Westfalen -Lippe were merged as "LÄK Nord-Rhein-Westfalen."

Table for the absolute number by groups and organizations (topic)

Organisation	Absolute Frequency	Threat	Tipping points	Sector-specific measures	Individual measures	Co-Benefits	Emissions Health care sector	Stop fossil fuels	Strengthened climate policy	Insufficiency of climate policy	Addressing climate protests	Participation in climate protests
State-Level Medical/Dental Associations	330	18	0	167	67	9	50	8	45	4	5	1
Landesärztekammer Baden-Württemberg	53	6	-	38	3	-	-	4	7	1	-	1
LÄK Bayern	35	1	-	8	20	1	-	2	3	2	1	-
LÄK Berlin	89	4	-	42	12	-	-	-	14	-	-	-
LÄK Brandenburg	-*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LÄK Bremen	23	-	-	9	8	1	-	-	1	-	-	-
LÄK Hamburg	44	-	-	31	4	-	-	-	3	-	-	-
LÄK Hessen	11	-	-	7	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
LÄK Mecklemburg-Vorpommern	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
LÄK Niedersachsen	11	1	-	5	2	3	-	-	3	-	4	-
LÄK Nordrhein- Westfalen*	29	4	-	11	8	1	-	-	6	-	-	-
LÄK Rheinland-Pfalz	2	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LÄK Saarland	7	-	-	5	2	1	-	1	3	-	-	-
LÄK Sachsen	11	1	-	4	1	-	-	-	3	-	-	-
LÄK Sachsen-Anhalt	6	2	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LÄK Schleswig-Holstein	15	-	-	5	2	-	-	1	2	1	-	-
LÄK Thüringen	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
Landes Zahnärztekammer Baden-Württemberg	2	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Bayern	4	-	-	1	3	2	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Berlin	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Brandenburg	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Mecklemburg-Vorpommern	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Niedersachsen	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Nordrhein	3	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Saarland	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Sachsen-Anhalt	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Schleswig-Holstein	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LZÄK Sachsen	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Members of the G-BA	45	6	-	22	3	3	-	2	15	-	-	-
Kassenärztliche Bundesvereinigung (KBV)	4	-	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Gemeinsamer Bundesausschuss (G-BA)	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Deutsche Krankengesellschaft (DKG)	17	3	-	10	-	1	-	2	11	-	-	-
GKV-Spitzenverband (GKV)	23	3	-	9	2	2	-	-	4	-	-	-
Kassenzahnärztliche Bundesvereinigung	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Health Insurance Providers	103	1	1	39	51	11	1	1	15	1	-	-
Techniker Krankenkasse (TK)	11	-	-	6	4	1	-	-	2	-	-	-
Allgemein Ortskrankenkasse (AOK)	22	-	-	5	18	4	-	1	5	1	-	-
Barmer Ersatzkasse (BARMER)	26	1	1	12	14	2	1	-	7	-	-	-
Deutsche Angestellten-Krankenkasse (DAK)	12	-	-	6	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
IKK Classic	13	-	-	7	10	2	-	-	1	-	-	-
Kaufmännische Krankenkasse (KKH)	19	1	1	3	4	2	1	-	-	-	-	-
Emergency Services	197	4	1	151	33	-	1	1	13	2	-	-
Deutsches Rotes Kreuz (DRK)	136	2	-	108	19	-	-	1	9	1	-	-
Malteser	26	2	-	14	11	-	-	-	-	1	-	-
Johanniter	35	0	1	29	3	-	1	-	4	-	-	-
Professional Political Interest Representations	124	12	-	65	20	2	-	2	37	3	3	-
Bundesärztekammer (BÄK)	64	2	-	24	1	-	-	2	22	3	1	-
Bundes Zahnärztekammer (BZÄK)	6	1	-	6	11	-	-	-	1	-	1	-
Hartmannbund	33	5	-	17	4	2	-	-	6	-	-	-
Marburger Bund	79	9	1	26	4	-	1	4	26	1	11	7
Bundespsychotherapeutenkammer (BPTK)	8	4	-	8	4	-	-	-	6	-	1	-
Bundesver. Deutscher Apothekerverbände (ABDA)	13	-	-	10	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
Bundespflegekammer	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subtotal	895	50	3	470	178	25	92	18	142	11	19	8
Other	103	6	0	18	9	0	2	3	12	2	3	3
AWMF	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Verbund unabhängiger Heilpraktiker (VUH)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bund Deutscher Heilpraktiker (BDH)	28	-	-	13	7	-	-	-	13	-	-	-
Ärzte ohne Grenzen Deutschland (MSF)	75	6	-	5	2	-	-	3	5	2	3	3
Total	996	56	3	488	187	25	95	21	154	13	22	11

* For better readability, results with entries marked as "-" were replaced.

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Example of a contribution analyzed according to formal and content categories.

Source:

https://www.instagram.com/p/CuOwjKqs_OF/

Formal category
date: 03.07.2023
source: Instagram

Thematic category
individual measures